

English-Major Students' Self-Reports on Their Experiences Using Video Self-Recording Technique

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 01, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: May 01, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : English Learning, Tertiary Student, Video Self-Recording Technique, Vietnam</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7883965</p>	<p><i>English teaching and learning quality have received remarkable attention from Vietnamese educators. Innovations in language teaching and learning are, therefore, encouraged. Video self-recording technique has been recommended to use in English classrooms. Nonetheless, studies on this technique have been limited in the Vietnamese context. Accordingly, this study was designed as a mixed-method approach to examine 195 Vietnamese tertiary students' perceptions of the technique's benefits in their language learning. The results from a questionnaire and 20 semi-structured interviews indicated the technique's remarkable contributions to students' development in both linguistics and non-linguistics aspects. Regarding non-linguistics-related benefits, the students perceived the technique to develop their learning autonomy, ICT literacy, and their use of non-verbal expressions. For linguistics-related benefits, the technique fostered their self-evaluation abilities, activated their background knowledge, and improved their English pronunciation. Based on the results, English instructors are encouraged to apply this technique in their classes.</i></p>

Introduction

Teaching and learning English are paid intensive attention to in the Vietnamese context. The Vietnamese government has made notable efforts to enhance the quality of teaching and learning English (Thao & Mai, 2020). For instance, many reforms at national and local levels have been promulgated. To enhance the quality of teaching and learning English, the Vietnamese government also encourages English teachers/lecturers to apply innovations to their classes (Hang & Van, 2020). They can experience the benefits and drawbacks of these innovations and then share their experiences with others. Consequently, Vietnamese teachers/lecturers use varied teaching techniques in their classes and introduce several valuable ideas to their colleagues. One of the ideas is to require English as a foreign language (EFL) students to record themselves on videos. The self-recording technique has been widely used in various teaching and learning contexts (Bergman, 2015; Silfia & Narius, 2012). However, there are still some concerns about whether it is helpful for EFL students or to what extent it helps them improve their English (Encalada & Sarmiento, 2019). Thus, it is essential to explore how the students who have experienced using this technique to learn English perceive the impact of this technique on their English learning. This current study was expected to give English-major students a chance to share their ideas about the impact of video self-recording techniques on their English learning in the Vietnamese context. This piece of writing promisingly helps its readers better understand the use of the technique. Moreover, it is a good chance for practitioners interested in this technique and innovations in English teaching and learning to compare the impacts of this technique to others. Also, using this technique in the Vietnamese context would give researchers an excellent chance to reflect on other teaching and learning contexts. Hence, this current study was employed to address a research question: "According to Vietnamese students, what are the impacts of video self-recording technique on their English learning?"

Literature Review

Self-Recording Technique

Self-recording on videos is a technique using media in language learning and teaching to facilitate EFL students to achieve better language competence. This technique is often used in English-speaking and listening classes. According to Allen (1983), self-recording on videos is a type of self-directed learning technique in which students will record themselves talking about a particular topic. Thanks to technological development, EFL students can use various tools to record themselves on videos, such as smartphones, laptops, tablets, etc. (Hariry, 2015; Juniardi et al., 2020; Sofiana & Mubarak, 2020). In the Vietnamese context, where most students own a smartphone, the technique is easy to use for English learning.

Benefits of Self-Recording on Video Technique

Many benefits of video self-recording technique have been found. According to Savaş (2012), using the self-recording video technique helps EFL students monitor their performances, self-evaluate their use of linguistics

and non-linguistics aspects, and be more critical. Bajrami and Ismaili (2016) highlighted the usefulness of this technique in enhancing EFL students' listening comprehension skills, developing their speaking competencies, improving their use of non-verbal expressions, and encouraging their motivation to learn English. In addition, according to the report by Çakir (2006), video recordings can help provide EFL students with authentic linguistics inputs; conceptualize their non-linguistic usages, such as facial expressions, movements, or looks; increase their communicative competence; meet their learning needs. Besides, there are many other studies on the positive effects of self-recording technique on EFL students' learning, such as making the learning process more interactive and exciting, encouraging students' participation (Prema & Kumar, 2018), promoting learner autonomy (Prema & Kumar, 2018; Amirnejad, 2015; Bahadorfar & Omidvar, 2014), developing students' language use in real-world speaking contexts (Pitarch, 2018; Irawati, 2016; Kavoshian & Ketabi, 2016), activating both background and new knowledge (Pitarch, 2018), developing students' language skills (Pitarch, 2018; McNulty, 2012; Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011; Knoll, 2014), increasing students' vocabulary and grammatical knowledge (Pitarch, 2018; McNulty, 2012), bettering students' speaking fluency, ICT literacy, pronunciation, and self-confidence, reducing English-speaking anxiety (Menggo et al., 2019), developing students' translating skills (McNulty, 2012), increasing students' self-evaluation skills (McNulty, 2012; Hakim, 2016; Muslem & Abbas, 2017; Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011; Knoll, 2014), allowing students to learn whenever and wherever they want (Menggo et al., 2019; Ozkan, 2013; Bahadorfar & Omidvar, 2014), fostering their learning motivation (McNulty, 2012; Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011), promoting cooperative learning (Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011, Knoll, 2014), and increasing students' awareness of self-responsibility (Ozkan, 2013). In conclusion, self-recording on video is a worth-trying technique because of its contributions to EFL students' language competence.

In this current study, the benefits would be divided into two clusters, including (1) linguistics-related benefits and (2) non-linguistics-related benefits. Figure 1 manifests the divisions.

Figure 1
Benefits of video self-recording technique

The framework allowed the research team not to explore the students' perceptions of the technique's benefits but also an excellent chance to examine whether the students gained more linguistics-related benefits than non-linguistics-related benefits. As a result, it entirely made the present study differs from the previous ones.

Methods

Research Design

The present study was conducted as a mixed-methods approach, using a questionnaire and 20 focus-group interviews to collect data. This design allowed the research team to collect data from many students to generalize the findings and gauge a deep understanding of their thoughts. As a result, the findings would be more significant.

Participants

The participants of this study were 195 tertiary students in the Mekong delta, Vietnam. Table 1 displays their general information.

Table 1
Participants' information

Variables		Number of participants
Gender	Male	59
	Female	136
Classification	Freshmen	128
	Sophomores	47
	Juniors	14
	Seniors	6
Majors	Non-English Majors	99
	English Majors	96

The participants included 59 males and 136 female students; 128 first-year students, 47 sophomores, 14 juniors, and six seniors; 99 non-English major students and 96 English majors. Significantly, the students confirmed they had experienced learning with the video self-recording technique. After the participants responded to the questionnaire, sixty out of 195 students were invited to participate in 20 focus-group interviews, three students each. In the Results and Discussion section, the interviewees were called by pseudonyms to keep their information confidential.

Data Collection Instruments

Questionnaire

The first instrument for data collection was a 22-item questionnaire. The questionnaire was self-developed by the research team. Specifically, to design the instrument, they reviewed and modified the findings presented in the previous studies (e.g., Amirnejad, 2015; Bahadorfar & Omidvar, 2014; Hakim, 2016; Irawati, 2016; Kavoshian & Ketabi, 2016; Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011; Knoll, 2014; McNulty, 2012; Menggo et al., 2019; Muslem & Abbas, 2017; Ozkan, 2013; Pitarch, 2018; Prema & Kumar, 2018). According to the framework of this study, the questionnaire included two main clusters: (1) linguistics-related benefits and (2) non-linguistics-related benefits. Table 2 details the questionnaire.

Table 2
Questionnaire

Clusters	Items	References
Linguistics-related benefits	1, 3, 8, 9, 13, 14, 15, 16	Bajrami and Ismaili (2016), Çakir (2006), Hakim (2016), Kim (2014), Kırkgöz (2011), Knoll (2014), McNulty (2012), Menggo et al. (2019), Muslem and Abbas (2017), Pitarch (2018), Savaş (2012)
Non-linguistics-related benefits	2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 11, 12, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22	Amirnejad (2015), Bahadorfar and Omidvar (2014), Bajrami and Ismaili (2016), Çakir (2006), Kim (2014), Kırkgöz (2011), Knoll (2014), McNulty (2012), Menggo et al. (2019), Ozkan (2013), Prema and Kumar (2018)

Besides, the research team left an "Others" item at the end of the questionnaire to give students a chance to add more ideas that are different from the existing items. The instrument was designed as a bilingual questionnaire writing the items in both Vietnamese and English. The purpose was to help non-English major students completely comprehend the items and provide them with an excellent chance to practice English reading. The questionnaire was piloted with 30 students who also had recorded themselves on videos to learn English. The Scale test was employed to check the reliability of the questionnaire. The test results were convincing to use the instrument to collect data in the actual study ($\alpha=.89$).

Focus-Group Interviews

The second instrument for data collection was focus-group interviews. This instrument allowed the research team to group some participants who shared common features related to the study's aims and scope. Notably, these students experienced their learning with the technique. They, therefore, have ideas to talk about the topic. The interview questions mainly focused on the students' perceptions of the benefits of the video self-recording technique. During the interviews, Vietnamese as the students' mother tongue was used to help the participants express their ideas quickly, comfortably, and comprehensively. The interviews were recorded on videos and carefully note-taken with participants' permission. The data collected from the interviews were then transcribed into English. If any unclear information was found, the research team would send emails or make direct phone calls to ask the students to clarify it. To ensure the quality of the transcriptions, the research team asked for help from an expert in translation and interpretation. The expert received, proofread, and edited the transcripts.

Data Analysis

The quantitative data were analyzed before the analyses of the qualitative ones. Remarkably, the research team used SPSS 20.0 to analyze. The Scale test was employed to check the reliability of the questionnaire. The results

showed that the data were reliable enough to conduct further analyses ($\alpha=.94$). Then, a Descriptive Statistics test was employed to examine the average mean score of students' perceptions of the technique's benefits. Later on, a Pair-Sample t-test was run to check which one the students benefited from the technique more, linguistics-related benefits or those related to non-linguistics aspects. Based on the noticeable results, such as the highest and lowest mean scores, the research team would gain a more profound understanding of students' perceptions in the follow-up interviews.

For the qualitative data, the research team used a thematic analysis approach. The procedures follow the steps. First, all members read through the transcriptions to get familiar with the data. Then, they classified the data according to themes as different positive effects of the video self-recording technique on the participants' learning. They inserted the data into a table with different benefit-based columns. After that, they compared their table to that of the other member. The similarities were kept; the team then discussed the differences. Also, the research team invited an experienced researcher in applied linguistics to be the referee. Accordingly, the referee's comments would decide what should be edited and kept and what should be deleted.

Findings and Discussion

Students' Perceptions of the Benefits of the Video Self-Recording Technique

First, the results of the Descriptive Statistics test on the students' general perceptions of the technique's positive impact on their language learning are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3

Benefits of video self-recording technique (N=195)

Benefits	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD
7. Developing learner autonomy	1.00	5.00	4.47	.74
16. Developing students' self-evaluation capacities	1.00	5.00	4.34	.79
9. Activating students' background knowledge	1.00	5.00	4.32	.71
13. Improving students' English pronunciation	1.00	5.00	4.30	.73
22. Developing students' ICT literacy	1.00	5.00	4.27	.76
15. Developing students' translating skills	1.00	5.00	4.23	.78
14. Developing students' listening skills	1.00	5.00	4.18	.82
3. Enriching students' lexicon and grammatical knowledge	1.00	5.00	4.14	.81
10. Meeting students' individual needs	1.00	5.00	4.11	.76
18. Bettering students' use of non-verbal expressions	1.00	5.00	4.11	.82
17. Enhancing students' learning motivation	1.00	5.00	4.08	.81
21. Increasing students' self-confidence	1.00	5.00	4.08	.77
8. Bettering students' use of authentic language	1.00	5.00	4.07	.88
5. Making lessons more interesting	1.00	5.00	4.06	.82
6. Enhancing students' engagement in classroom activities	1.00	5.00	4.05	.81
20. Reducing students' speaking anxiety	1.00	5.00	4.05	.86
1. Increasing students' speaking competencies	1.00	5.00	4.04	.79
19. Developing students' collaborative learning	1.00	5.00	3.99	.84
4. Making students' process more interactive	1.00	5.00	3.97	.91
11. Providing flexibility in learning in terms of time	1.00	5.00	3.72	1.16
2. Increasing students' awareness of self-responsibility	1.00	5.00	3.52	.92
12. Providing flexibility in learning in terms of place	1.00	5.00	3.51	1.19
Total	1.00	5.00	4.09	.60

As observed, the students highly perceived the technique's benefits in their English learning ($M=4.09$). The results were in line with several previous studies (e.g., Amirnejad, 2015; Bahadorfar & Omidvar, 2014; Hakim, 2016; Irawati, 2016; Kavoshian & Ketabi, 2016; Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011; Knoll, 2014; McNulty, 2012; Menggo et al., 2019; Muslem & Abbas, 2017; Ozkan, 2013; Pitarch, 2018; Prema & Kumar, 2018). Most Vietnamese students show positive attitudes towards using media in their English learning (Nguyen & Habók, 2022). As a means of using media in language learning, self-recording on videos to study English is, therefore, welcomed in English classrooms in Vietnam. In the interviews, some students stated,

“To me, this technique is fascinating. I like something like this because I can feel my improvement after doing video self-recording tasks.” (August; Male)

“I like this technique because it is exciting. I have never felt bored when I do tasks with this technique...” (May; Female)

According to the excerpts, self-recording videos was an interesting technique for the students. As a result, it made the lessons or students' learning process more enjoyable. It was similar to the study by Prema and Kumar (2018), which indicated the abovementioned benefit of the technique.

Among 22 items, Item No. 17 “*Developing learner autonomy*” obtained the highest mean score ($M=4.47$), followed by those of Item No. 16 “*Developing students' self-evaluation capacities*” ($M=4.34$), Item No. 9

“Activating students’ background knowledge” (M=4.32), Item No. 13 “Improving students’ English pronunciation” (M=4.30), Item No. 22 “Developing students’ ICT literacy” (M=4.27), Item No. 15 “Developing students’ translating skills” (M=4.23), Item No. 14 “Enriching students’ lexicon and grammatical knowledge” (M=4.14), Item No. 18 “Bettering students’ use of non-verbal expressions” (M=4.11), Item No. 10 “Meeting students’ individual needs” (M=4.11), Item No. 21 “Increasing students’ self-confidence” (M=4.08), Item No. 17 “Enhancing students’ learning motivation” (M=4.08), Item No. 8 “Bettering students’ use of authentic language” (M=4.07), Item No. 5 “Making lessons more interesting” (M=4.06), Item No. 6 “Enhancing students’ engagement in classroom activities” (M=4.05), Item No. 20 “Reducing students’ speaking anxiety” (M=4.05), Item No. 1 “Increasing students’ speaking competencies” (M=4.04), Item No. 19 “Developing students’ collaborative learning” (M=3.99), Item No. 4 “Making students’ process more interactive” (M=3.97), Item No. 11 “Providing flexibility in learning in terms of time” (M=3.72), and Item No. 2 “Increasing students’ awareness of self-responsibility” (M=3.52). The mean score of Item No. 12 “Providing flexibility in learning in terms of place”, was the lowest one (M=3.51). Unlike their perceptions of the flexibility of place when doing video self-recording tasks, the students were significantly aware of the following benefits of this technique: enhancing students’ self-confidence, learning motivation, the effectiveness of non-verbal usages, lexicon and grammatical knowledge, listening and translating skills, ICT literacy, pronunciation, self-evaluation capacities, and especially learner autonomy. Besides, the technique remarkably helped them meet their individual needs and activate their background knowledge. Interestingly, eight responses offered “Increasing students’ reading and writing skills” as another benefit of the technique in the “Others” item.

Developing Learner Autonomy

In the interviews, the students appreciated the contributions of the technique to their development of learner autonomy. Sparks and Ronnie said,

“I can do the video self-recording tasks by myself without bothering others. Especially, I can do whatever I want. Of course, the video is relevant to the topics my teacher assigns the class to do... After re-watching my videos, I can easily recognize my mistakes. As so, I would like to redo the task.” (Sparks; Male)

“Doing these tasks is very interesting because I can record myself on videos with my style. These tasks allow us [students] to set up our plans, angles, and more... The more I do these tasks, the better my speaking skills are. Therefore, I want to do these tasks more in the future.” (Ronnie; Female)

The development of the students’ learner autonomy as a benefit of video self-recording tasks was similar to several previous studies (Amirnejad, 2015; Bahadorfar & Omidvar, 2014; Prema & Kumar, 2018). Video self-recording tasks do not require language teachers to interfere in the students’ learning or task-doing process. As so, the students will have their own space to use their creativity to complete the tasks and enhance their independent learning. According to Sheering (1991), students’ independence in their learning is positively correlated to their learner autonomy. Therefore, the more students are required to work independently, the more they develop their learner autonomy. The video self-recording technique, accordingly, is helpful for students’ learner autonomy as it requires the students to work independently.

Developing Students’ Self-Evaluation Capacities

According to the discussions in the focus-group interviews, the technique seemed to be great for developing the students’ self-evaluation abilities. Barbara and Tatum remarked,

“I have never been satisfied with myself the first time I recorded myself on videos to discuss a topic because I usually make many mistakes. Thanks to video self-recording tasks, I recognize that my pronunciation is not good. As a result, I practice to improve it as much as possible.” (Barbara; Female)

“This technique [video self-recording technique] is better than all other techniques in evaluating my skills and knowledge. I can watch myself and check whether I make any grammatical mistakes or pronunciation. Consequently, I re-record myself to have a better product.” (Tatum; Male)

The video self-recording technique provided the students with an excellent opportunity to reflect on their work. As a result, it developed their capacities to evaluate their learning progress. It was similar to some previous studies (e.g., McNulty, 2012; Hakim, 2016; Muslem & Abbas, 2017; Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011; Knoll, 2014). However, some students were not comfortable when others watched and assessed their products. Tee stated,

“It is okay to watch yourself on videos and reflect on the performances. However, I am not really... happy to hear from someone talking about my videos. However, these experiences also help me gain more motivation to learn. Besides, I can better my self-evaluation skills which will be very helpful for my future performance.” (Tee; Male)

The above excerpts also explained why the students did not highly perceive the technique to develop their cooperative learning (M=3.99). It was different from the studies by Kim (2014), Kırkgöz (2011), and Knoll (2014). Those authors indicated that promoting cooperative learning is one of the most noticeable benefits of the video self-recording technique. Most Vietnamese students have moderate or high self-esteem, so they always try their best to avoid losing face (Quynh, 2021). Hence, it will prevent them from welcoming others to watch their videos if they are not confident in the quality of their products.

Activating Students' Background Knowledge

To record a high-quality video talking about a specific topic, the students had to reflect on their living experiences. Don and Linlin remarked,

“Making a good video is not easy at all. I have to review my background knowledge about the topic. The knowledge will become the main source of my ideas. Then, I search on the Internet to enrich the ideas...” (Don; Male)

“I have watched many videos made by my classmates. Compared to observably innocent, inexperienced friends, those who look more mature made better videos. Therefore, I preferred watching my mature friends' videos to others because I could learn many things from them and their videos. I am not sure, but living experiences or background knowledge significantly differed them...” (Linlin; Female)

Activating students' background knowledge is one of the significant findings in the study by Pitrach (2018), which aimed to investigate the impacts of the video self-recording technique on language teaching and learning. A video is valued as high-quality or low-quality because of the quality of its images, sounds, and content as well (Okubo, 1992). In the Vietnamese context, the word “age” in the proverb “With age comes wisdom” does not mean “age” but “living experience”. This emphasizes how important background knowledge is to students' learning process. Similarly, Jekosch (2006) highlighted how speakers' background knowledge steers their perceptions of a particular topic. For students with a strong background knowledge foundation, their messages can carry deeper meanings than those of less experienced background.

Improving Students' English Pronunciation

Their perfectionism sometimes required the students to record themselves multiple times for a good video. As so, they had more chances to practice their speaking and pronunciation. Bobby and Jennie said,

“I do not want to upload a low-quality video and someone will watch it. Therefore, I usually record a video more than 3 or 4 times to select the best version... I try to make my speaking as natural as possible by using different types of intonation, not just flat ones.” (Bobby; Male)

“I want my videos to be perfect, or at least, they are perfect to me. It often takes me 2 or 3 hours to have a good-enough video... I do not find it bad because I have more chances to practice my speaking skills and English pronunciation. The more I watch my videos, the more mistakes in pronunciation I can find. As a result, I practice pronouncing these words to improve them.” (Jennie; Female)

Repeating a speech will help students improve both speaking skills and pronunciation (Scarborough et al., 1977). Recording a video requires students who are perfectionists to watch themselves on the videos and re-record if they find the products under their expectations. As a result, the video self-recording technique was helpful for the students' English pronunciation in this current study. In the same vein, Menggo et al. (2019) highlighted the positive effect of the technique on language learning in their research.

Developing Students' ICT Literacy

Video self-recording technique requires students to have some research on the use of ICT in their learning. Cherry and Candice said,

“It is useful for my ICT skills. Recently, there have been a lot of video-recording applications. They have filters, effects, and so on. I often use TikTok to record my videos. It is an amazing application for video-recording...” (Cherry; Female)

“The self-recording tasks require me to work with ICT most of the time. After doing these tasks, I know a lot of new things related to ICT. I can use more applications to support my learning...” (Candice; Female)

According to the excerpts, using this technique gave the students an excellent opportunity to apply more tools to learn English. Accordingly, they widened and broadened their knowledge of ICT. The results were similar to the study by Menggo et al. (2019). Candice's excerpt remarked on her great awareness of the influence of technological development on her language learning. Regarding the rapid growth of technology, there are many valuable tools for language learners to enhance their learning achievements (Ahmadi & Reza, 2018). For that reason, it is vital to meet language learners' demand for using ICT in learning and teaching to help increase their perceptions of a particular technique's effectiveness. Accordingly, the students well perceived their development of language and ICT competencies when recording themselves on videos with various applications.

Developing Students' Translating Skills

Even though the technique requires the students to practice oral skills, such as speaking and listening, they must prepare a good script to make their videos worth watching. Kathy and Sue said,

“It is not easy to have a good video. No one wants to watch a video with nonsense messages. Therefore, I must carefully think about what I should say in my video and write them in a note. I usually use Google Translate to support my transcriptions. Some sentences translated by Google Translate are under my expectations. Therefore, I use them as a base to enhance their quality by my translation...” (Kathy; Female)

“I usually write my ideas in Vietnamese first and translate them later... As a result, my range of vocabulary is more significant. I can find my translation skills too much better than before.” (Sue; Female)

As stated, a video’s content is as important as its quality of images or sounds. Therefore, language learners also paid significant attention to preparing an excellent script to enhance the quality of the content while doing video-recording tasks. According to Kathy’s and Sue’s excerpts, as English is not their mother tongue, they had to prepare their scripts and translated them into the target language. Through the process, their translating skills were remarkably practiced due to new vocabulary they learnt during the process. As a result, it is understandable that the students perceived their translating skills to be developed thanks to the video self-recording technique. The results were in line with the study by McNulty (2012).

Developing Students’ Listening Skills

In the interviews, the students highlighted the influence of follow-up tasks, which required them to watch others’ videos and give feedback, on enhancing of their listening skills. Philip and Eren said,

“Our lecturer requires us to watch others’ videos and give feedback on their performances. I think it is also a good chance to practice my listening skills because I can figure out the mistakes my friends usually make and fix them for myself. These mistakes in grammar and pronunciation help distinguish words and sounds that will definitely help me in future listening tests.” (Philip; Male)

“There is always a follow-up task after uploading the videos to Google Drive. The task requires us [students] to watch and notice speakers’ mistakes. It benefits me because I can avoid my friends’ mistakes in my videos. I usually write down the mistakes in my friends’ products.” (Eren; Male)

The excerpts indicated the improvement of listening skills when the students watched their classmates’ videos. Similarly, several previous studies highlighted the positive impact of this technique on language learners’ listening skills (e.g., Bajrami & Ismaili, 2016; Pitarch, 2018; McNulty, 2012; Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011; Knoll, 2014). Furthermore, the students’ excerpts showed a need to provide them with a further practice task after recording themselves on video. Remarkably, the students in this current study were required to give feedback on others’ performances. As a result, they developed their language skills, especially listening skills. Bijami et al. (2013) found it advantageous to ask language learners to give peer feedback on each other’s products.

Enriching Students’ Lexicon and Grammatical Knowledge

Like translating skills, lexicon and grammatical knowledge are highly demanding if students want to have an excellent script and record a good video. Susan and Long remarked,

“Sometimes, I lack the vocabulary to write scripts for my videos. Therefore, I look up the dictionaries, such as Oxford or Cambridge, to find useful words or phrases. After recording a video, I learn more vocabulary and functional language. It is amazing!” (Susan; Female)

“It is embarrassing to say a sentence full of errors. Therefore, I must carefully prepare my scripts regarding word choice or grammar. Consequently, I have significantly bettered my lexicon and grammatical knowledge....” (Long; Male)

To speak well, language learners must have a wide range of lexicon and grammatical knowledge (Conboy & Thal, 2006). The video self-recording task is a language-speaking activity (Allen, 1983). Therefore, it requires language learners to enhance their range of vocabulary and grammar use. Thus, the students developed the needed skills. It was similar to the studies by Pitarch (2018) and McNulty (2012), indicating that the technique is helpful for language learners’ lexicon and grammatical knowledge.

Meeting Students’ Individual Needs

Although the students were assigned to talk about a particular topic, they had different perspectives. Mixi and Norton stated,

“After watching my friends’ videos, I recognized we had different perspectives of a particular topic. As a result, I learned a lot from them...” (Mixi; Female)

“I learned a lot from my friends because they had different ideas from mine...” (Norton; Male)

Mixi continued,

“We [students] have different strengths and weaknesses. For example, I usually make mistakes in grammar use, but Chou [a student] lacks ideas to talk. We have to develop different skills to complete our video self-recording tasks....” (Mixi; Female)

Through the recording process, they had a chance to self-evaluate their proficiency and knowledge (McNulty, 2012; Hakim, 2016; Muslem & Abbas, 2017; Kim, 2014; Kırkgöz, 2011; Knoll, 2014). Therefore, they recognized their strengths and weaknesses and determined their different learning paths for further improvement. Consequently, the determination would help students meet their individual needs to become successful language learners (Çakir, 2006).

Bettering Students’ Use of Non-Verbal Expressions

It will not be fascinating if students sit still and talk about a topic without non-verbal expressions. Cindy and Clara remarked,

“It is a perfect chance to improve my facial expressions or movements. The videos will be very boring if I speak unemotionally...” (Cindy; Female)

“I have to act like I am talking to the viewers. I realize that non-verbal language is fundamental to be a successful speaker after doing video self-recording tasks...” (Clara; Female)

Wharton (2009) affirmed that bodily gestures while one is speaking sometimes are more important than verbal language. Non-verbal language like facial expressions or body movements can help deliver the messages effectively, even beyond the speakers’ expectations. As a speaker in their videos, the students had to deliver their stories, messages, or thoughts to the viewers adequately. Therefore, it is mandatory to use and improve the effectiveness of their non-verbal language use for video self-recording tasks. The positive effect of the technique on language learners’ non-verbal expressions was highlighted in the study by Bajrami and Ismaili (2016).

Enhancing Students’ Learning Motivation

Interestingly, although video self-recording tasks took students much time to complete, they gained significant motivation for learning English. Paul and Majutele remarked,

“It takes so much time to record a video. I have to watch it again and again before deciding whether to publish it or not. However, it is interesting to do these tasks because they are meaningful. Moreover, it will be wonderful if your teacher highly grades your videos. Amazing!” (Paul; Male)

“I often spend one or two hours recording a video that I find qualified enough to upload to Google Drive. It takes time... much time. However, I know why my lecturer wants us [students] to do these tasks. They are so helpful for our English learning, and they are interesting as well. Nothing is better than doing things to help my English learning better, and the technique is wonderful.” (Majutele; Female)

According to the excerpts, the students recognized the technique's effectiveness in their English learning. Accordingly, they did the video self-recording tasks with positive attitudes even though the tasks took them so much time and effort. Recognizing a technique’s positive impact on students’ learning encourages them to learn and develop (Moskowitz et al., 1985). Therefore, the advantages of the video self-recording technique increased the students’ willingness to complete the tasks and their motivation for language learning. Bajrami and Ismaili (2016) also found the same results in their study.

Increasing Students’ Self-Confidence

The positive impact of the technique on the students’ self-confidence, especially in speaking, was also a remarkable finding of this current study. Meg and Mikoto said,

“I used to be very shy to speak in public, especially in English. However, after recording myself on videos and receiving positive feedback from my friends and lecturer, I am now not shy anymore...” (Meg; Female)

“I become more confident in myself than I used to. Recording myself on videos helps improve my public speaking skills. Now, I can speak confidently in front of my friends and my lecturer...” (Mikoto; Female)

The findings were similar to what Menggo et al. (2019) indicated in their study. Notably, after doing video self-recording tasks, the students enhanced their self-confidence. However, this current study also found that the video self-recording technique is helpful for shy students to speak out and develop their public speaking skills. Moreover, Meg’s excerpt highlighted the importance of positive feedback on students’ English learning. Mackey (2006) affirmed a positive correlation between teachers’ and peers’ positive feedback and students’ language learning. However, there should be profound considerations for feedback on students’ performances as it is a double-edged knife. If the students perceived the feedback as accurate, they would appreciate and develop; otherwise, they would be negatively affected if the comments were meaningless and incorrect (Nicholas et al., 2001).

Increasing Students’ Reading and Writing Skills

The video self-recording technique mainly focuses on students’ speaking and listening skills. Therefore, it was interesting to hear that the students perceived the technique to impact their writing skills significantly. Duane explained,

“Preparation stage is critical to have a good video. For instance, we [students] have to write a script including our ideas for speaking. As a result, it is a good chance for practicing our writing skills...” (Duane; Female)

In the same focus group interview, Tommy added,

“I can recognize my improvement in writing skills as I have more vocabulary and a better understanding of grammatical knowledge. Therefore, it does not develop my speaking and listening skills only, but my writing and reading skills also...” (Tommy; Male)

The students did not expect to develop their reading and writing skills after learning English with the video self-recording technique, but it worked. The finding differed from previous studies, which indicated that the technique is helpful for oral performance only (e.g., Menggo et al., 2019; Muslem & Abbas, 2017; Pitarch, 2018; Prema & Kumar, 2018). However, according to the excerpts, the students wrote to speak, not to test their writing performance. Though the enhancement of vocabulary and grammatical knowledge was observed to be

helpful for their speaking performance, it was not easy to check whether their writing skills improved significantly or not. Speaking and writing are not the same or even wholly different (Woolbert, 1922).

Providing Flexibility in Terms of Place – as the Least Perceived Benefit

In the interviews, the students also explained why they did not feel comfortable recording themselves on videos when they were at home. Richards and Vivian said,

“For the self-recording tasks, we [students] can record ourselves wherever and whenever we want. It is great. I usually do my tasks at home. Nonetheless, when I record myself at home, many things, noise or others, happen, negatively affecting the videos' quality. Therefore, I have to do it again and again. It takes much time...” (Vivian; Female)

“I have to find somewhere with beautiful views to help increase the quality of my videos. I do not want others to see my house because it is not really... big or beautiful as expected. Therefore, I do not find it comfortable to record myself at home. However, I do not have many choices like cafeterias because I do not have much money....” (Richards; Male)

According to the excerpts, the students were very self-demanding as they wanted to maximize the quality of their videos. It was similar to the Ozkan (2013) study, which indicated that the video self-recording technique dramatically impacts students' awareness of self-responsibility. Their videos will not be viewed by themselves only but by their classmates and their lecturer. Consequently, they have to do their best to protect their face. Also, in Vivian's case, the quality of videos was negatively affected by many factors, especially noise. Filming, accordingly, requires a lot of effort and time to eliminate noise and interruptions (Ayala & O'Connor, 2013). However, time-consuming is a big problem for Vietnamese students because they must learn several school subjects weekly. As a result, they cannot spend much time on only one subject or task (Vu & Shah, 2016). In Richard's case, living conditions affected his perception of the technique's benefits, especially the flexibility of place for video recording. Due to monetary issues, Richard could not go to the cafeterias with beautiful views to record himself on videos. Consequently, he struggled while doing the video-recording tasks. In the Vietnamese context, many students encounter monetary issues (Bui et al., 2019); the technique, therefore, needs profound considerations before language teachers are likely to use it in their classes.

Linguistics-Related Benefits versus Non-Linguistics-Related Benefits

Table 4 displays the results of the Paired-Sample T-test examining whether there was a significant difference between the students' perceptions of linguistics-related benefits and those of non-linguistics-related benefits.

Table 4

Linguistics-related benefits versus non-linguistics-related benefits

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Ling - Non-Ling	.20	.37	.03	.15	.25	7.77	194	.00

The results indicated a significant difference between the students' perceptions of linguistics-related benefits and non-linguistics-related benefits that the technique offered ($p=.00$). In the interviews, the students affirmed that they had gained some the non-linguistics-related benefits of the technique but the technique's positive impact on their improvement in linguistics aspect was the main reason why they liked this technique. Donnie and Cara said,

“It is conducive for my ICT skills because I have to work most of the time with computer or technological devices to complete the video self-recording tasks. I like it. However, the best of this technique is still its impact on my language skills, especially speaking and listening. I recognize my significant improvement in these skills after doing these tasks...” (Donnie; Male)

“I am a major English student, so I must focus on my language skills and knowledge. Therefore, I do not particularly appreciate doing something not useful for my study. Fortunately, this technique works well on my language skills...” (Cara; Female)

Similar to the previous studies, which have found a positive impact of the technique on students' linguistics and non-linguistics skills and knowledge (e.g., Menggo et al., 2019; Muslem & Abbas, 2017; Pitarch, 2018; Prema & Kumar, 2018). However, almost none has paid attention to how different language learners perceive the technique to affect their linguistics and non-linguistics skills and knowledge. The difference found in this current study indicated that the technique is more beneficial for students' linguistic improvement than their development of non-linguistic aspects. According to the excerpts, the students would accept a particular teaching and learning technique if they recognized its positive effects on their language improvement. It was similar to the study by Itmeizeh (2016), which argued that students are likely to make use of particular learning techniques when students recognize the positive effects of the techniques on their learning achievements.

Conclusion

The study was conducted as a mixed-method approach to investigate 195 tertiary students' perceptions of the effect of the video self-recording technique on their English learning. The findings encouraged educators to use the technique in their English classes as the students highly perceived the positive impact of the technique on their language improvement. The study highlighted some benefits of the technique found in the previous research, such as developing students' learner autonomy, self-evaluation capacities, English pronunciation knowledge, translating skills, ICT literacy, listening skills, lexicon and grammatical knowledge and use of non-verbal expressions. Besides, the technique also activated students' background knowledge to complete tasks, helped them meet their individual learning needs, and significantly improved their reading and writing skills. Additionally, the students perceived the technique to be more helpful for their linguistics-related development than their improvement in non-linguistics-related aspects.

Implications

The observable benefits offer many implications for enhancing the quality of English teaching and learning. First and foremost, the technique is strongly recommended in English classes as a further practice task because language learners need to have their own space to be creative and produce good products. Secondly, peer feedback as a follow-up task should enhance students' cooperative learning, listening, and evaluation skills. However, the teachers interested in the technique should remind the students that the primary purpose of this task is not to harm others' faces but to help each other improve. As so, a guideline for giving feedback on others' products should be introduced to the students. Thirdly, before assigning language learners to record themselves on videos, the teachers need to be aware of the importance of students' living experiences in their video production. Hence, the teachers should find a suitable way to provide students with good background knowledge or activate their existing knowledge about the topic to help them work more effectively. Fourthly, the technique is helpful for students' English pronunciation. Thus, it is strongly encouraged to use for teaching and/or testing students' pronunciation. Fifthly, English teachers should allow their students to use different applications for recording their videos as the students are likely to be more familiar with the rapid change of technology than the teachers can be. Sixthly, the technique can be considered a good tool for developing students' translating skills. Accordingly, students majoring in English translating and interpreting should have a chance to experience this technique to learn in the English translation classes. Last but not least, students need a wide range of lexicon knowledge before doing the video self-recording tasks. Therefore, there should be a sufficient provision of useful vocabulary for the assigned topics to help improve the quality of students' videos. Moreover, English teachers must investigate their students' differentiations to provide adequate support and avoid discouragement.

Limitations and Recommendations for Further Studies

Although the study found many significant findings related to the benefits of innovation in English teaching and learning, it still has room for further improvements. The study focused on students' self-reports about the video self-recording technique; the study, therefore, lacked real-world evidence to indicate the technique's actual benefits. Consequently, further studies should use other data collection instruments such as observations and students' videos to analyze the technique's substantial impact on students' learning. Besides, this study focused on investigating students' perceptions only. Accordingly, it is necessary to explore teachers' perceptions of the technique to know why they use it in their classes. Additionally, intensifying the number of participants will help figure out more significant findings and generalize these findings. Moreover, further studies are recommended to investigate the technique's impact on language students' reading and writing skills since it is often used in speaking and listening skills courses only. Finally, challenges students and teachers face while using this technique in teaching and learning should be well-presented to help improve its effectiveness.

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